

Formation of Smart Contracts and Liabilities Imposed on Business

Enas Mohammed Ali Qutieshat

Assistant Professor, Faculty of Law, Philadelphia University

Dr. Bassam Al-Tarawneh

Assistant professor, Faculty of Law, Philadelphia University

Abstract

This paper aims to identify the practices involved in the formation of smart contracts and the limitations that are faced by the organizations through development of smart contracts in business. The Smart contract is developed based on specific criteria in the business. The smart chain in the business identify the block chains that are developed in the business to resolve different financial issues in the company. In this report, the elements of smart contracts are evaluated and analyzed along with a discussion of previous researchers on the same criteria. This study identifies that smart contracts become essential for business practices with development of technology. The form of smart contracts has captured the attention of legal attorney and its impact on contract law of business. This report implements the descriptive methodology approach in which the secondary data is analyzed to identify the formation of smart contracts and its liability on business. Additionally, the research data is analyzed through secondary qualitative analysis.

Keywords: Smart contracts, Liabilities, Cryptocurrency, Blockchains, Bitcoin.

1. Introduction

This report is based on the formation of smart contracts in the business and its impact on the development of various business contracts and liability that is imposed on business. The main focus of this report is to identify different business elements that are involved in the formation of smart contracts in the business. The concept of Smart contracts is defined as the self-executing contracts which develop the terms of agreement between the buyers and sellers. This form of contracts includes the agreement of different business partners in the block chains [1]. The formation of Smart contracts is based on a collection

of code and data that is combined together with the specific address on the blockchain. It has been found from the study of Kosba, et al. (2016) that smart contracts have attained significant attention in the legal aspect of the business. The reason for this is that the smart contracts have an impact on contract law and lawyer. Fairfield (2014) indicated that smart contract help the business to reduce the involvement of third party in development of contracts which reduce the conflict in the business. The smart contracts completely transform traditional business process into a digital contract through development of blockchain in the business structure [4]. In the smart contract process, it starts with conversion of currency into a program which is based on coding system the most commonly used currency in this smart contracts is cryptocurrency which is based combining different currency into one single digital currency [2]. This enables two parties to exchange goods and services physically through payment with digital medium.

Background

In a business contract, it is important to value business or obligatory right that guarantees the creditor right to demand from debtor fulfillment of a given benefit. In this case, the responsible person is determined. Personal rights are transient and becoming extinct by compliance or other forms [5]. Similarly, in the smart contracts, the business is liable to ensure the payment or receipt of the services. The doctrine of liability defines contract as the legal bond that gives the active creditor subject such as the right to demand from the debtor, who is responsible for the payment, and fulfillment of a given benefit. In the essential relationship, there may be more than one active subject and more than one passive subject. The smart contracts are defined as the implementation of artificial intelligence in development of contracts. These

contracts hold the great potential for strengthening the business relations and reduce the need of traditional

paperwork, various cost and involvement of lawyers for facilitating trust among business partners [6]. It is important for the business, to identify the difference in contract with business responsibility. Knapp, Crystal and Prince (2016) indicated that the contract is a duty or a commitment assumed and derives from a legal bond, arising from the law or act of the will, which compels business to give something economically appreciable, for the benefit of others. Already the responsibility stems from the non-fulfillment of the contract, being thus a legal consequence of transmissible environment [5]. In this context, it has been found that contracts are intrinsically linked; there may be any contract without liability that includes debts in an organization are arising from gambling, prescribed debts [7]. In these cases, debt exists, but debtor cannot be executed due to unethical or illegal nature of work. On the contrary, Lauslahti, Mattila and Seppälä, (2017) defined the liability without a contract in business as the liability of the guarantor, who although assumed responsibility, has no contract to pay the debt unless there is default of the main debtor.

Problem of the Study

The commercial distribution is a vast sector of economic activity involving diversified schemes of action that is implying a variety of legal forms. In this form of business practices, discrimination is possible through segmentation of reality, which is often revealed, as involvement of artificial intelligence is formation of contracts [1]. Conversely, it has been found from the study of Luu, et al. (2016) that the traditional method of contracts increase conflict of interest and higher involvement of lawyers in the business practices. Furthermore, smart contracts are deeply dynamic that is subject to continuous adaptation to the changing circumstances. About this, the productive processes of the organization are under the influence of technological innovations. It is essential for the business to transform the mode of contracts into digital medium.

Research Questions

Based on the above discussion of smart contract formation and the liability imposed on business, the following research question included are answered to complete the study:

1. How are the smart contract formed in the business?
2. What are the liabilities that are imposed in the business practices through formation of smart contracts?

3. What is the impact of the smart contract on business practices?
4. What is the difference between smart contracts and traditional contracts in the business?

Objectives of the Research

The aim of this study is attain based on the following objectives:

1. To identify the process of smart contract formation in the business.
2. To determine liabilities that are imposed in the smart contract formation of the business.
3. To evaluate the impact of smart contract on business practices.
4. To recognize the difference between smart contracts and traditional contracts in the business.

2. Significance of the Study

Through technological development in the global business world, it is essential for every business transform different business practices into digital method. The smart contracts formation support for business development and reduce the involvement of external parties in the business [8]. It has been found that there is fewer research are made for supporting formation of contracts in the businesses. In this context, the various elements that support for successful execution of smart contracts are rarely identified in academic research. This research identifies significance of smart contract in business practices. Idelberger, et al. (2016) pointed out transformation of mode of currency support for attaining simplifying operational practices. Furthermore, this research identifies various liabilities that is imposed on business through adaptation developed technology in the business. It has been found that there is limited literature currently available that lacks a discussion of legal implications in business practices of smart contract formation. To fill the gap of the literature, this study provides the initial analysis of legal business aspect that supports for smart contract formation.

3. Literature Review

Smart Contract Formation

It has been found from the study of Omohundro (2014) that formation of smart contracts is one way of organizing the provision of products and services to the public that constituting a legal category with relatively indefinite outline. This development in organization designation brings together diverse legal framework, which precisely serves the purpose of bringing the products of the business to the end user.

Based on the study of Knapp, Crystal and Prince, (2016) it has been found that as an organizational form, distribution contracts are halfway between the firm and the market. i.e., the contract between full vertical integration where the disposal of the products is carried out by organized means that is owned and

controlled by the producer. Additionally, it may be between sole alternative for the wholesalers and independent retailers. In essence, smart contracts are form of hybrid organization, which involves the specialization of economic agent [9]. This outcome includes the distribution of risks of production and marketing.

Importance of Smart Contract Formation

Smart contracts formation are sometimes referred to as enhancing the cooperation links which business establish between legally autonomous economic agents at different levels of the production and distribution chain in the organization [12]. In this context, Omohundro (2014) suggested that through smart contracts in the organization, the distributor joins a business network, which is organized and controlled by the producer. From this point of view, there is a clear distinction between the distribution agreements of the business and other liability contracts. The distribution contracts may serve distribution purposes, which may be beginning with the purchase and sale but lack precisely distinctive feature. The smart contracts develop the distributor network of products with the particular manufacturer. In contrast to this Zheng, Xie, Dai and Wang (2016), indicated that in distribution and supply chain network of the business products are organized (economic and legal) and distribution contracts are in contrast with the organizational arrangements led and controlled by the supplier, such as purchases and distributor groups of businesses.

Elements of Smart Contracts

Peters and Panayi (2016) found that the treatment of private distribution contracts gives rise uncertainties as to their appropriateness and practical justification in the business environment. The contractual practices of the organization with its business partners provided support to the situation, which is only made worse by the fact things are viewed from perspective of competition law. Indeed, the uncertainty stemming in the European Union results in arbitrary application of agency contract regime to other contracts, which adds complexity of fair competitive environment in which the contracts are developed internally in the organizations [9]. In this context, the smart contract of business is based on blockchains which are the simple

concept in which the chain of transactions occurs in relation to each activity. The blockchain basics elements include two different elements that include transactions and block which are further discussed below:

Transactions

The blockchain of the business is based on a transactional database which is accessible by everyone in the database of whole network. Delmolino (2016) specified that if the business wants to change the business element, it must require making transactions which are adopted by all participant to transform any business activities.

Blocks

The other element of blockchain is the blocks which are referred to overcome different obstacles in the business [8]. In relation to this, the term Bitcoin is alternatively used for overcoming the attack of double spending on smart contracts. The blocks are used to overcome the impact of double transactions in the business through development of blocks.

Liabilities Imposed on Business

In most of the European countries, the smart formation of liability becomes an essential business element [2]. In this contract, the commercial business agency has its legal regulations. Through these contracts, many elements are responsible for transposing business contracts into the national legal order. This has provided the uniform guidelines of European law outlined in Council Directive [11] One of the essential motivations of discipline that is accepted by the businesses without any doubt is the social promotion of commercial agents. Given the nature and characteristics of the commercial managing operations and central role the liability contracts play in the business, it would be expected that the legal system would give greater flexibility to the respective regulations that recognizing interested broad freedom of business formation [10]. In practice of smart liability contracts in the organization, there is a clear tendency to extend business procedures at least in parts. The protective discipline of the business contracts and other agreements support for attaining business goals efficiently. In this regard, the European legal theory and case-law have largely accepted the involvement of artificial intelligence in development of contracts that the commercial contract must be governed by provisions of the contract system which has the greatest similarity with it: the distribution contracts of business [4].

Impact of Brexit on Smart Contracts Formation

Financial analysts remain uncertain about the magnitude of the effects of the UK's future exit from the European Union ("Brexit") on the global economy. This Brexit legitimately raises many questions and fears from the main economic partners of the United Kingdom that affect the business in the country [14].

Seventh largest customer in the UK and its fifteenth largest provider, Moroccan politicians and economists appear to be reacting with pragmatism for the moment and perceive Brexit as an opportunity to develop closer and personalized direct trade links with Great Britain without the intermediation of the European Union [15].

Clauses of Business Contracts

These only cover the period up to the granting of financing and transfer the underlying asset. These contracts in business apply throughout performance [16]. The clauses of business contracts are classified in the following:

Hardship Clause

The clauses of Hardship are present in commercial agreements or partnerships whose execution spread over a long period. This clause of contracts allows the signatory parties to demand a new negotiation be opened when an economic or technological event occurs that upsets the initial balance of contract. Wilson (2016) indicated that it is important for a business to note that these clauses of business have a more limited effect than other. This clause only imply a renegotiation is not respected resolves itself in damages without any right of the exit of the part undergoing the economic imbalance.

Force Unavoidable Clauses

The clauses of Hardship are valid in business practices also appropriate for all the clauses having a vocation to manage the effects of the occurrence of unforeseeable events and independent of the will of the parts on the execution of their obligations suspension, delay, and exemption [17]. For future contracts in business contracts, business partners who consider that certain consequences of Brexit may constitute in their regard events of force unavoidable economic and political clearly specify this in the business contract.

Clauses of Change of Law

These clauses, which are very common in financing documents, large-scale projects, public-private partnerships and, more generally, transnational operations, allow the parties to waive certain liability guarantee, payment and even renegotiate certain clauses. In this regard, Fairfield (2014) specified that smart formation of contract in the business when a change in the legislative framework occurs during the life of business contract with partners that modifies the original scope of their commitment.

Currency Risk Clauses

These clauses required to be reviewed with the greatest attention when organization involved in international business. Fluctuations in the pound sterling are anticipated introducing currency hedging instrument that is influenced directly or indirectly by the price of the pound sterling [7]. According to Knapp, Crystal and Prince (2016), that this clause support to overcome the effects of Brexit, it is advisable to insert these clauses of a business contract to specify the commitments that continue to apply between business partners.

Arbitration Clauses

Regarding the applicability to of arbitral awards made in the the United Kingdom and Brexit have no major impact because the two Kingdoms are parties to the New York [16].The clauses of arbitration before the International Chamber of Commerce have a second wind. Finally, all clauses referring to the European Union as a reference territory in franchising, distribution, and non-competition or exclusivity agreements will have to be revised to take account of Brexit in order to include the United Kingdom.

4. Methodology

The purpose of this research is to identify the smart formation of contracts and its influence on business liabilities. In this study, the methodology of the research is based on descriptive research approach that supports for collecting data and analyze the data based on previous researches. Through qualitative analysis of research data different outcome of business is identified. The qualitative secondary data analysis enable the researcher to identify reliable and accurate data that identify the impact of smart contract on business practices. The application of qualitative research analysis, a different element of block chains and its impact on business is identified.

5. Results

It has been identified from the study of Bhargavan, et al. (2016) that smart contract is based on different key elements that include capital markets, sale of digital

assets, smart government and supply chain management through development of block chains at digital platforms. In contrast to this, specified that smart contract formation includes certain level of risk which require a business to developed careful plan for mitigating risk. In this context, Idelberger, et al., (2016) pointed out that company used different proactive measure for overcoming the impact of risk on business practices with the effective product development and maintaining a good association with business partners that are included in the blockchain of

the company. In the absence of any agreement in its current legal order, it is the World Trade Organization regime with the establishment of customs and tariff barriers. These would apply in a business scenario in which the UK renegotiate trade agreements based on WTO's global agreements.

The unpredictable currency fluctuations caused by the fall of the pound sterling make Brexit impact on business practices [15]. In contrast to this, O'Hara (2017) identified that Brexit has a positive impact on free trade agreements on which the economic equilibrium of many contracts of business is based on. However, uncertainty in business practices remains as to the entry into force of such agreements. The use of Hardship clauses will be a means of adapting contracts to new regulatory constraints that have hitherto been unpredictable and irresistible. The process of smart contract formation is based on the following cycle:

Figure 1: Cycle of Smart contract Formation (Source: capgemini.com)

According to the study of Fairfield (2014) that the term smart contract is widely used and sometimes misused by different businesses. This term is perfectly fit in the situation where general contract language is transformed into computer languages through coding and data transformation. In relation to this, Dai, Mahi, Earls and Norta (2017) identified that it is important

for the business to identify whether the business contracts are transformed effectively in digital practices or not. Apart from this, Idelberger, Governatori, Riveret and Sartor (2016) indicated different elements that are used in the formation of smart contract that include emergence of block chains with bitcoin. Conversely, Delmolino et al. (2016) specified that smart contract formation enhanced business ability to developed more complex contracts that is simply transformed into smart contract language. Through this, the development of smart contract in business not only support business

practices but it also facilitates all the partners in block chains distribution process of the company.

However, smart contract applications vary across different practices in which basic elements remain same. The formation of smart contract enables companies to take proactive measure for reducing potential risk in the business and overcoming the impact of liability exposure. The difference in the traditional and smart contract is presented in the following figure:

Figure 2: Difference Between smart contracts and Traditional contracts

The main difference in traditional contracts and smart contract is based on digital formation of contracts [8]. In contrast to this, Peters and Panayi (2016) pointed out that development of different digital protocol in business developed different opportunities for growth and expansion and applied as a tool to increasing business efficiencies. On the other hand, Idelberger et al. (2016) shown in his study that smart contracts are presenting the semantic representations that identify the level of liability in the business and different partners. Furthermore, it has been found that there is any legal issue that is identified through smart contract in which the business offering services based on digital contracts elements [12].

6. Discussion

Based on the analysis of different literature it has been found that the situation of business is far from satisfactory from application of smart formation practices in developing contracts. Indeed, the trend towards uniformity of the legal regime applies to different types of distribution contracts, which involve suppliers as business partners. These contracts reflect a clear simplification of reality and devaluation of distinctive characteristics that exhibit in such formation of contracts. In contrast to this, Wilson (2016) pointed out that the legal treatment of smart

contracts is heavily influenced by models of analysis that have underlying pre-understandings of reality, which do not correspond effectively to actual legal requirement of business contracts. Based on the study of Dai, Mahi, Earls and Norta (2016) it has been found that Development of smart contracts results in recovery of smart contract idea that increases its popularity for supporting business process and increase efficiency in development process of the business.

For instance, the paradigm of existence that marked difference in economic power between organizations and business partners, which allegedly would determine the need for enhanced protection through application of smart contracts. Such a stance in business practices leads to a regulatory model that significantly contradict business efficiency and gains that are generated by vertical agreements which are making contracts less interesting and leading to disintermediation [19]. Apart from this, is in view that smart formulation of contracts is not consistently followed in all the Member States of the European Union. This creates an environment of strong uncertainty, which can decisively affect investment and intra-Community trade [17]. Moreover, the simplistic nature of the dominant analysis model has become evident with the emergence of smart contracts in business, where the relation of forces such as business stakeholders is reversed.

Based on the analysis of Delmolino (2016) it is recognized that the emergence of blockchain and cryptocurrency support for attaining higher business return in business practices. In this context, Omohundro (2014) identified various benefits of cryptocurrency application in operational activities. Conversely, Zheng, Xie, Dai and Wang (2016) identified that various liabilities that are associated with the smart formulation of contracts is based on variation in programming of a digital system that results in mistakes of programming of digital contracts. From the analysis of Gao and Singh (2014)

study which specified that the legal issues of smart contract formation. This include product liability, quality of services, protection of information, maintaining confidentiality, reliable trade practices and support for maintaining cybersecurity among the business partners of block chains that are involved in smart contract formation with the business.

In view of the fact, that this is not uniformly followed in all the Member States of the European Union [13]. Through this, it creates an environment of strong uncertainty, which can decisively affect investment and intra-Community trade of the organization. The sophistication and globalization of markets, coupled with new frontiers opened by e-

commerce, call for a reorientation of the legal discipline of distribution contracts.

According to Bhargavan, et al. (2016) it has been specified that several European directives continue to be applied or transcribed by the United Kingdom. In this context, smart contract formulation is an important business element for reducing the impact of Brexit on the business practices. In addition, the United Kingdom can draw on existing schemes such as the Norwegian models which make entry into the European Economic Area allowing it to benefit from the free movement of persons, Switzerland agreement that supports for bilateral free trade agreements, or Turkish for developing new customs union. Through this, business development practices are enhanced in the UK, and for sustainability, it becomes important to manage the business resources.

7. Conclusion

It has been concluded that smart contract formation is an efficient mode of transforming the business agreements into a digital medium. From the result of various literature, it has been found that adaptation of smart contracts enables businesses to reduce exposure to risk. Furthermore, through involvement of digital currency, the process of distribution become smooth. In this context, it has been found that smart contract formation reduces the involvement of lawyers in business procedures and also support for enhancing contract complexity. In contrast to this, this study identified that with the development of technology the legal issues would continually evolve. It is predicted that smart contract will provide more support to businesses and involve different elements to disrupt technological and legal perspectives. Although, the liability imposed through adaptation of business practices will remain same the companies with effective implementation of digital process can effectively reduce the impact of risk while offering product and services through a digital medium.

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